

THE LENGTH-WEIGHT RELATIONSHIP AND CONDITION FACTOR OF *Protopterus annectens* (OWEN) IN
GBEDIKERE LAKE, BASSA, KOGI STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

A total of sixty two samples of *Protopterus annectens* (Owen) were examined for this study from Gbedikere Lake in Bassa Local Area of Kogi State between August and November 2008. The length-weight relationship calculated for species gave a b-value of 2.55 which is indicative of negative allometric growth. It attained a length of 59cm and weight of 397g. The condition factor varied from 0.23 to 0.76 with a mean of 0.39 ± 0.08 and shows that the fish is well and in good environment for growth and survival.

KEYWORDS: *Protopterus annectens*, allometric growth and survival.

INTRODUCTION

Fish found in tropical and sub-tropical water system experience frequency growth fluctuations due to factors such as food composition changes, environment changes, rate of spawning to mention but a few, length weight relationship can be used to assess the influence of these factors in fish. Kulbicki *et al*, (1993) and King (1966) reported that fish growth, mean weight of a given body length of fish estimation and the relative well being in fish can be known through this relationships length-weight relationships studies have been done in different water bodies and on different fishes. Notably among these are the report of King (1996) on some Nigerian fresh water fishes, Taiwo and Aransiola (2001) on *Chrysichthys* species in Asejire Lake, Fafioye and Olujajo (2005) on five fish species in Epe Lagoon, Nigeria and Laleye (2006) on *Oreochromis niloticus* in Oeume River in Benin.

Protopterus annectens commonly known as African lungfish is the only species of primitive family Lepidosirenidae found in West African fresh waters (Reed *et al*, 1976). Holden and Reed (1972) reported that the ancient fish did not form any significant part of commercial catches and that the flesh is tasty but many traditional taboos prevent the eating of the species.

The study present information on the length-weight relationships and the condition factor of this valuable fish species is in order to aid the management in the lake.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Lake Gbedikere is a natural lake located between Latitudes $3^{\circ}24^{\circ}$ and Longitudes $5^{\circ}14^{\circ}$ and is about 10km to the East of Oguma the Head quarter of Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Water enters the Lake from tributaries that run from River Benue during rainy or flood season. When the season is over, the Lake separates out. The Lake is about 450m north of Gbedikere village. The water body covers about 400 – 450m and a depth of 10 – 14m deep, depending on the season.

The lake used for fishing; consequently most of the settlers around the Lake are fishermen (Upper Benue River Basin Development Authority, 1985). The lake experience two seasonal periods; the rainy season starts in the month of May and last till October and is characterized by heavy down pour which sometimes have an extensive flood action. The dry season is from late October to April and is characterized by cold, dusty -dry wind followed by intense heat. The Lake contains fish, other aquatic animals and some macrophytes such as wire grass (*Cyperus articulatus*) which are used for weaving mats.

SAMPLES COLLECTION

Fish samples were identified and collected from the fishermen catches using gill nets and Malian traps between August and November 2008. Total length (cm) and weight (g) were taken using measuring board and top loading balance. Length-weight relationship was calculated using the formula:
 $W=aL^b$ which was transformed to logarithm of the form

$$\text{Log } W = \text{Log } a + b \text{ log } L$$

Using instat statistics package
 Where W= body weight of the fish (g),
 L=total body length of fish (cm)
 a and b=values estimated by regression formula.

The condition factor (K) was calculated using the

$$K = \frac{100w}{L^3} \text{ (Pauly, 1984)}$$

Where K= condition factor, L=Total body length of fish (cm)
 W=body weight of fish (g).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A total of sixty two species of *Protopterus annectens* were collected for the study. The total length ranged between 22.30cm and 59.2cm with a mean of 34.27 ± 6.33 and weigh between 19.70g and 397.9g with a corresponding mean of 158.0 ± 78.97 (Table 1). This shows that the specie used for the study were relatively matured.

Table 1: Summary of length and weight distribution of *Protopterus annectens* in Gbedikere Lake, Bassa Local Government Area, Kogi State.

Species	N	Total Length (cm)			Body weight (g)		
		Min	Max	Mean±S.D	Min	Max	Mean±S.D
<i>Protopterus annectens</i>	62	22.30	59.20	34.27±6.33	19.70	397.90	158.00±78.97

Condition factor (CF), parameter of a, b and r of the length weight relationship of *Protopterus annectens* is shown in Table 2 and Fig 1.

Table 2: Condition factor (CF) of *Protopterus annectens* in Gbedikere, Lake, Bassa Local Government Area, Kogi State.

Parameters	Values
A	0.0183
B	2.552
R	0.9229
Mean condition factor (CF)	0.39±0.08

a, b = regression coefficient; r = correlation coefficient

The exponent of (b) value of 2.553 shows that *Protopterus annectens* exhibits negative allometric growth this indicate that growth in length increase as weight increases and also the rate of increase in body length is not proportional to the increase in body weight. This result is different from the one obtained by Oniye *et al* (2006) when he obtained the b-value for male and female *P. annectens* in Jachi Dam near Katsina in Katsina State, Nigeria to be 3.12 and 3.22 respectively. This could be due to the condition of the fish caught during different season, location, sex, sample site and nature of the water body. The regression coefficient of 0.9229 compares favourable with the 0.86 and 0.84 obtained by Oniye *et al*, (2006) for *P. annectens* male and female respectively which suggest

that the findings of this study is valid. Fafioye and Oluajo (2005) also obtained a condition factor of 1.00 for some other fish specie from Epe Lagoon.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The composition of both sexes gave a better overview of length-weight relationship and condition factor of *Protopterus Annectens*. The result of this study show negative allometric growth pattern, the b-values were generally in agreement with results for fishes of the same genus obtained from other geographical areas. Confirming that Gbedikere Lake in Bassa, Kogi State is a good environment for the growth, reproduction and survival of the species. The study provides basic information on the length-weight, length-length relationship and condition factor of *Protopterus Annectens* that will be useful for fishery biologist and managers in Nigeria.

The in-depth studies on the length-weight, length-length relationship and condition factors; and other aspect of biology and biodiversity of *Protopterus Annectens* towards sustainable management in Gbedikere Lake Bassa, Kogi State should be further elucidated.

Fig 1: Length- weight relationship of *Protopterus annectens* in Gbedikere Lake Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State.

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